

**EFFECTIVENESS OF DON BOSCO'S EDUCATIONAL PHILOSOPHY IN
THE EMPOWERMENT OF THE TRIBAL YOUTH IN THE
EASTERN GHATS**

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Abstract

Tribal people have innumerable problems. Govt. of India is doing many thought oriented programmes to empower them. The Don Bosco's Educational philosophy and its institutions are doing yeoman services to them. The present investigator being a father working in the Don Bosco's Institutions though of exploring the Don Bosco's educational Philosophy and its institutions for uplifting the living conditions of tribal people. Hence, it has become the natural quest of the investigator to explore the level of effectiveness of Don Bosco's educational philosophy in the empowerment of the tribal youth in the Eastern Ghats. The objective of the study is to find out the Effectiveness of Don Bosco's Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats. The investigator has developed and validated a tool to find out the effectiveness of Don Bosco's Educational philosophy in the empowerment of tribal youth in the Eastern Ghats. The tool developed by the investigator with 14 items was used for the study. In this study stratified random sampling technique was used to select 474 tribal youth studying in degree colleges from five revenue mandals namely Chintapalli, Koyyuru, Paderu, Golgonda and Narsipatnam of Vishakapatnam district. The finding of the study is the effectiveness of Don Bosco Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats is good. The Don Bosco's Educational society is doing a good job in elevating the plight of tribal youth in Vishakapatnam district.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Don Bosco's Educational Philosophy, Empowermen, Tribal Youth, Eastern Ghats.

1. INTRODUCTION

Famous Indian and Western philosophers and educators had the vision of human excellence. There existed a firm faith that when heart and hand work with head, there will be completeness in education since vedic times, the overall trend of intellectual transactions was based on religious philosophy, thoughts and ideals which predominantly focus on human person. Education is as old as the human race. It is never ending process of inner growth and development and its period stretches from cradle to grave. Education to humanize humanity.

Don Bosco (1815-1888) is an educationist who revolutionized the system of education. His contribution to education was immense. It aimed at the transformation of the individual.

Don Bosco written a book on "*The Preventive System in the Education of the Young*". Don Bosco philosophy of education addresses most of the challenges posed by materialism, relativism, consumerism and individualism. And it is very relevant in modern times. It is in fact a philosophical system which is very significant today. For Plato principles are the root source of knowledge and being. For Aristotle and Thomas Aquinas, the principles are the fundamentals that govern our knowledge, the way of being and acting. These principles define the *modus operandi*, a way of proceeding. They enable us to orient ourselves in thought and action, leading us to get a clearer understanding of the purpose of life. It is in this sense that we can talk of Don Bosco's philosophy of education. Don Bosco sees education as a process of transformation activity of the individual. It consists in sharing of faith, human experiences, transmission of knowledge and values, fostering critical thinking and reflection, all done in a loving environment. For Don Bosco a teacher is not merely someone who imparts knowledge. A teacher is the one who like a *guru* accompanies the students. He/she leads by example. A teacher plays an important and an indispensable role in the process of education. The students pick up right values, attitudes and a vision of life from their teachers. This pedagogy demands respect for the young person, for his greatness and his frailty, for his dignity.

2. CONCEPTUALFRAMEWORK

India has the single largest tribal population in the world. This constitutes 8.6 per cent of the total population of the country (Census of India, 2011). Education and empowerment is indispensable for helping tribal peoples cope with national integration. Education will also determine their prosperity, success and security in life. The tribes which remain either deprived of or negligent toward education will suffer the consequence.

For us 'education' is an integral part of the empowerment process. Empowerment of the tribal community means capitulating tribal communities to secure access and control of their land, forest and water resources as well as sustains and promotes viable alternatives for security of their livelihoods.

Empowerment thus is an interactive process whereby tribal communities are enabled to participate actively in local governance (decision making that affects their own life situation). It is in this context that we need to define the role of adult education. Salesians of Don Bosco – Roman Catholic Missionaries – arrived in Pedaboddepalli – Narispatnam of Visakhapatnam – Andhra Pradesh. Through a first-hand account of the activities initiated by the Don Bosco Mission, we are introduced to adult education, based on the philosophy that “major learning in the tribal context takes place through struggles on issues focusing on human rights of tribal communities” The word 'empowerment' is not used in a rhetorical sense here, but becomes the guiding principle behind the educational processes developed: in terms of setting up appropriate organizational structures, identifying and responding to specific need of different groups of tribal women, men, children and youth. and developing new training approaches.

3. REVIEW OF THE RELATED STUDIES

Maanhvizhi Emayavaramban, et al., (2020) conducted a study on Barriers in the Educational Attainment of Tribal Girl students in Salem District of Tamil Nadu State, India. Result revealed that lack of public transport, poor staff pattern, unavailability of basic infrastructure facilities like road, the curriculum that does not provide support for their poor economic conditions, with very little scope for vocational education formed barrier for educational attainment.

Lal Kumar Singh and Shikha Banerjee (2019) conducted a study on A Study of Parental Involvement among Tribal Students with Reference to Anuppur District of Madhya Pradesh. The result supports that there is significant difference in the level of parental involvement between male and female tribal students. The difference found is in the favour of female tribal students.

4. NEED FOR THE STUDY

Tribal people have innumerable problems. Govt. of India is doing many thought oriented programmes to empower them. The Don Bosco's Educational philosophy and its institutions are doing yeoman services to them.

The present investigator being a father working in the Don Bosco's Institutions thought of exploring the Don Bosco's educational Philosophy and its institutions for uplifting the living conditions of tribal people. Hence, it has become the natural quest of the investigator to explore the Effectiveness of Don Bosco's Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats.

5. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is to find out the Effectiveness of Don Bosco's Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats.

6. HYPOTHESIS FORMULATED FOR THE STUDY

The hypothesis of the study is the Effectiveness of Don Bosco's Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats is average.

7. INSTRUMENTATION

The investigator has developed and validated a tool to find out the effectiveness of Don Bosco's Educational philosophy in the empowerment of tribal youth in the Eastern Ghats. The tool developed by the investigator with 14 items was used for the study.

8. ESTABLISHMENT VALIDITY OF THE TOOL:

The investigator decided to test the effectiveness of Don Bosco's educational philosophy in the empowerment of tribal youth in the Eastern Ghats. The investigator prepared a tool with

18 items to ascertain the effectiveness of Don Bosco's educational philosophy in the empowerment of tribal youth in the Eastern Ghats. The investigator in order to test the tool supplied the tool to degree college students studying in Eastern Ghats. The investigator received feedback and suggestions from experts to check problems. The items which were not effective in revealing the effectiveness of Don Bosco's educational philosophy were eliminated. Finally the tool was constricted to have only 14 items.

9. ESTABLISHING THE RELIABILITY OF THE TOOL

The tool was administered among 40 degree college students studying in Eastern Ghats. After a gap of fortnight the tool was re-administered among the same 40 degree college students studying in Eastern Ghats. Pearson's product moment correlation was applied to the scores. The correlation value out was 0.91. It is a high level of correlation. Thus the reliability of the tool was ensured.

10. SCORING

The response to each specific problem was given in Yes or No type. The total score will be 14. Thus the scoring was done for all the questions. Descriptive was done.

11. SAMPLE DESIGN

In this study *stratified random sampling technique* was used to select 474 tribal youth studying in degree colleges from five revenue mandals namely Chintapalli, Koyyuru, Paderu, Gollgonda and Narsipatnam of Vishakapatnam district.

12. DATA ANALYSIS

H1:-The Effectiveness of Don Bosco's Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats is average.

TABLE: 1-DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS FOR THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DON BOSCO'S EDUCATIONAL PHILOSOPHY IN THE EMPOWERMENT OF THE TRIBAL YOUTH IN THE EASTERN GHATS

Qn.No.	Question	Yes		No	
		N	%	N	%
1.	Are you aware of the services of Don	400	84.38	74	15.62

	Bosco College?				
2.	Do you know educational philosophy of Don Bosco?	351	74.05	123	25.95
3.	Do you know Don Bosco Preventive System of education?	276	58.22	198	41.78
4.	Have you received any benefit from don Bosco centres of empowerment?	389	82.06	85	17.94
5.	Any one from your family/village in women self-help programs started by Don Bosco College?	342	72.15	132	27.85
6.	Are you aware of Don Bosco Integral Tribal Development Services?	356	75.10	118	24.90
7.	Did you receive primary education program from Don Bosco?	400	84.38	74	15.62
8.	Are you the student of Don Bosco Institutions?	400	84.38	74	15.62
9.	Do you know youth empowerment programs at Don Bosco College?	348	73.41	126	26.59
10.	Do the youth go for jobs after training at Don Bosco Tech.?	400	84.38	74	15.62
11.	Do you know skill India?	387	81.64	87	18.36
12.	Are you aware that Don Bosco College is collaborating with Skill India to empower the youth?	359	75.73	115	24.27
13.	Do you like to work in urban areas after getting training?	349	73.62	125	26.38
14.	Do you like to solve the problems of the village community?	474	100	0	0

It is evident from Table 1 that the all tribal youth studying in degree colleges (100%) want to give solutions to the problems of village community. 84.38 % of tribal youth studying in

degree colleges are aware of the services of Don Bosco educational institutions for tribal youth while remaining 15.62 % of tribal youth are not aware of it. 84.38 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have received primary education from Don Bosco institutions while remaining 15.62 % of tribal youth have not received it. 84.38 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges were students of Don Bosco institutions while remaining 15.62 % of tribal youth were not students of it. 84.38 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have stated that students go for job after getting training at Don Bosco Tech. while remaining 15.62 % of tribal youth do not get. 82.06 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have received benefits from Don Bosco centres of empowerment while remaining 15.62 % of tribal youth have not received such thing. 82.06 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have received benefits from Don Bosco centres of empowerment while remaining 17.94 % of tribal youth have not received such a thing. 81.64 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have known about skill India programme while remaining 18.36 % of tribal youth have not known about it. 75.73 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges do have awareness that Don Bosco is collaborating with skill India to empower the youth while remaining 24.27 % of tribal youth have not known about it. 75.10 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges do have awareness of Don Bosco Integral Tribal Development Services while remaining 24.90 % of tribal youth have not known about it. 74.05 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges do have awareness of Don Bosco's educational philosophy while remaining 25.95 % of tribal youth have not known about it. 73.62 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have stated that they want to work in urban areas after getting training while remaining 26.38 % of tribal youth do not want to work in urban areas after getting training. 73.41 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have stated that they know the youth empowerment programmes at Don Bosco College while remaining 26.59 % of tribal youth do not know the youth empowerment programmes at Don Bosco College. 72.15 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have stated that they have one from their family or village in women self-help programmes started by Don Bosco College while remaining 27.85 % of tribal youth have stated that they do not have any one of their family members or from their village in women self-help programmes started by Don Bosco College. 58.22 % of tribal youth studying in degree colleges have stated that they know Don Bosco preventive system of education while remaining 41.78 % of tribal youth have stated that they do not know Don Bosco preventive system of education. It may be inferred from the above finding that the effectiveness of Don Bosco Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats is good.

FIGURE 1 : BAR DIAGRAM SHOWING THE DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS FOR THE EFFECTIVENESS OF DON BOSCO’S EDUCATIONAL PHILOSOPHY IN THE EMPOWERMENT OF THE TRIBAL YOUTH IN THE EASTERN GHATS.

EFFECTIVENESS OF DON BOSCO'S EDUCATIONAL PHILOSOPHY

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13. FINDING OF THE STUDY

The effectiveness of Don Bosco Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats is good. The Don Bosco's Educational society is doing a good job in elevating the plight of tribal youth in Vishakapatnam district.

14. EDUCATIONAL IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

The effectiveness of Don Bosco Educational Philosophy in the empowerment of the Tribal Youth in the Eastern Ghats is good. The services rendered by Don Bosco's Educational Society are known to tribal people. The Don Bosco's Educational society is doing a good job in elevating the plight of tribal youth in Vishakapatnam district. Many more Non-Government Agencies should come forward to uplift the poor, downtrodden and tribal people.

15. CONCLUSION:

The study aimed at exploring the attitude levels of tribal youth. It will certainly help not only the researcher but also all the teachers, social workers and philanthropists who are on to help the tribal youth. The study also reveals models for tribal youth to be the entrepreneurs and honest citizens of the country. The study also reveals one to develop skills and aptitudes. I am trying to present appropriate procedure to have education and empowerment.

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